

score

D9.11 - SCORE Info Day

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
EBA	Ecosystem-Based Adaptations
ECCA	European Climate Change Adaptation
EWS	Early Warning System
LL	Living Labs
NPV	Net Present Value
SIP	Score ICT Platform

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 coastal city living labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Basque Country, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening *EBA* and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organizations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

The aim of this document is to report on the organization of the SCORE Infoday, which is the final event of the project organized as a side event of the 7th European Climate Change Adaptation conference (ECCA 2025) on 17 June 2025.

The SCORE project recognized the significant anticipation surrounding the ECCA 2025, which is the premier forum for exchanging practical solutions, sharing knowledge, and fostering collaboration on climate adaptation across Europe. Organised biannually since 2013, ECCA is a vibrant platform for exchange between adaptation researchers, practitioners, policymakers and other stakeholders. With the objectives to mobilize and link the community of climate adaptation and to share cutting-edge research, best practices, innovative solutions, and implementation experiences, ECCA has been chosen by SCORE project partners as a perfect venue to host the SCORE final event and to network with experts and specialists in the field.

In addition to the Final Event, SCORE hosted a booth in the exhibition area on 17-18 June 2025, where project partners showcased the smart technologies developed throughout the project. Live demonstration sessions were organised, offering participants the opportunity to discover and experience these innovative tools firsthand. The booth fostered networking opportunities with other projects and to exchange good practices with people working on climate adaptation.

All in all, the SCORE participation in ECCA was a success, with several new contacts established, dissemination material distributed, and almost 60 people attending the SCORE final event.

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

This deliverable is part of the Work Package 9 (WP9) which is a transversal work package integrating the results of all the WPs for the dissemination, communication, and exploitation process: it ensured that the outputs and learnings arising from all the activities of the project were visible to a wider audience, could be learned from and implemented on a European scale.

This deliverable is directly linked to the activities carried out within all Work Packages, since the objective of the final event was to present the main key achievements of the project. In fact, the SCORE final event organized at ECCA 2025 was the perfect opportunity for partners to share their experiences and discuss the challenges and successes of their work within SCORE during the past four years.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The SCORE final event «**Innovative solutions for climate change adaptation in coastal areas: when Green and Digital tools meet Living Labs**» was organised as a side event of the [European Climate Change Adaptation Conference \(ECCA\)](#) taking place on 16-18 June 2025 in Rimini (Italy). This event represented a key opportunity for the SCORE project to gain visibility and showcase its results at the European level, as it marks the conclusion of four years of work on climate resilience in European coastal cities.

ECCA is the leading conference for adaptation in Europe. The theme of ECCA 2025 “Smarter, Faster and More Systemic Adaptation”, aligned perfectly with the SCORE project’s mission to promote Ecosystem-Based Approaches (EBAs) supported by smart technologies and co-creation processes and provided the project optimal visibility at the European level, facilitating the dissemination of SCORE key achievements.

The SCORE final event took place on the second day of the ECCA, on 17 June 2025, with two sessions addressing:

- **Session 1:** Co-Creation & Living Labs – Rethinking Climate Adaptation
- **Session 2:** Data-Driven and Nature-Based Adaptation – Tools for Today and Tomorrow

Each session featured presentations by partners, followed by a panel discussion bringing together all partners, to share hands-on experiences, discuss the scalability and transferability of solutions, and explore how to bridge the gap between data, policy, and local implementation. SCORE partners presented the key project results, focusing on co-creation and living labs, as well as data-driven and nature-based adaptation tools for coastal cities.

Alongside the final event, the **SCORE project hosted a booth at the ECCA conference on 17–18 June**. The aim of this booth was to engage directly with attendees and exchange with those interested in the project’s work. It offered a great opportunity to showcase SCORE’s results and innovations, notably through live demo sessions where participants could explore the different technological tools developed throughout the project. These interactive demonstrations allowed visitors to get hands-on experience with the tools and better understand how they support climate resilience in coastal cities.

Before selecting ECCA 2025 as a venue for its final event, the SCORE consortium carefully considered other options, such as the European Maritime Day held in Cork (Ireland) in May 2025. While this event gathers a large network of stakeholders involved in maritime affairs and European coastal initiatives, its primary focus is on maritime affairs and sustainable blue Economy. The thematic alignment and potential audience engagement were therefore not considered optimal for showcasing the project’s outcomes and discussing its legacy. Another option was to organise an independent final event in Brussels, aiming to reach European decision-makers and institutional stakeholders more directly. However, this option presented several limitations. Beyond the significant logistical efforts it would require, the risk was to attract a more limited audience, lacking the diversity of stakeholders, essential for exchanging best practices and lessons learned. Additionally, hosting the event independently would have meant missing the valuable synergies and networking opportunities offered by being part of a major European conference, where SCORE could contribute to collective discussions on adaptation policies and methodologies.

2. SETTING AND AGENDA

The SCORE final event aimed to showcase the key outcomes, experiences, and lessons learned from the project, while opening a space for dialogue on the future of climate adaptation in coastal areas. The objective was to highlight practical and innovative solutions developed and implemented within the SCORE Living Labs and through the collaborative efforts of project partners, and to position these approaches within the broader context of European and international climate resilience strategies.

The workshop was divided into 2 sessions:

- 1) Co-Creation & Living Labs – Rethinking Climate Adaptation,
- 2) Data-Driven and Nature-Based Adaptation – Tools for Today and Tomorrow.

Each session was followed by a panel discussion with all presenters, with the opportunity for the audience to ask questions and share their own experience. The overview of the agenda is presented in Table 1, while each session is summarised in more details below.

The themes chosen for the two sessions, as well as the organisation of the panel discussions, were carefully designed to address all critical dimensions of the project. These included citizen engagement and co-creation methodologies, ecosystem-based approaches, data-driven climate risk modelling, smart monitoring tools, and the integration of green and digital solutions. This comprehensive approach guaranteed that the workshop covered the project's most significant outcomes and operational insights essential for ensuring the sustainability and future adoption of the SCORE methodology and tools.

Table 1: SCORE final event agenda

Session 1: Co-Creation & Living Labs – Rethinking Climate Adaptation	
14:00 – 14:10	Welcome and Introduction to the SCORE Project (Salem Gharbia, ATU Sligo, Ireland)
14:10 – 14:17	Embedding Co-Creation in Climate Resilience: SCORE's Living Labs (Charmae Pyl Wissink-Nercua, IHS, The Netherlands)
14:17 – 14:24	Citizen Science and Stakeholder Engagement Tools (Chiara Cocco, UCD, Ireland)
14:24 – 14:30	Ecosystem-Based Approaches: Catalogue and Evaluations (Luís Campos Rodrigues, ENT, Spain)
14:30 – 15:00	Panel Discussion: Living Labs in Action – Experiences from the Field (Moderator: Rochelle Caruso, ERINN, Ireland)
Session 2: Data-Driven and Nature-Based Adaptation – Tools for Today and Tomorrow	
15:00 – 15:14	Modelling Climate Risks in Coastal Cities to Strengthen Resilience with Data Driven Strategies (Paola Ceresa, RED Spa, Italy)
15:14 – 15:21	Smart Tools and Real-Time Monitoring (Michele Sacco, Consorzio LaMMA, Italy)
15:21 – 15:50	Panel Discussion: From Data to Action – Integrating Green and Digital Solutions (Moderator: Giovanni Serafino, MBI Srl, Italy)
15:50 – 16:00	Closing Remarks & Next Steps (Salem Gharbia, ATU Sligo, Ireland)
16:00 – 16:30: Interactive live demos of SCORE tools	

2.1. Co-Creation & Living Labs – Rethinking Climate Adaptation

The first session of the workshop was opened with a speech by Salem Gharbia, Project Coordinator at ATU Sligo (Ireland). Salem presented the background and context for the SCORE project, and the work done in the four-year project duration, including its impact and the legacy it will leave behind.

As the principal investigator of the SCORE project, Salem stated,

“As we bring this four-year journey to a close, we do so with optimism and pride. SCORE leaves behind a lasting legacy of tools, knowledge, and empowered communities — a legacy built on science, innovation, and the power of collective action. The momentum we have created will, I believe, continue to grow.”

“Our hope is that the SCORE experience will inspire further initiatives, big and small, across Europe and beyond — because the need for resilient coastal cities has never been greater. And when, in the years to come, we see coastal communities standing stronger against storms and rising tides, when citizens remain engaged, and when nature is recognised as an essential ally, we will know that the work we started here has truly made a difference.”

Salem stated few things, which could be considered

Figure 1: First session of the SCORE final event

Charmae Pyl Wissink-Nercua from HIS (The Netherlands) presented the **Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) concept** which is at the heart of SCORE: ten real cities where people co-designed ways to make their communities more resilient. These "living labs" are more than test sites: they're places where citizens, researchers, policy makers, and businesses collaborated to come up with ideas that fit their unique environments, such as restoring rivers or installing early warning systems.

Chiara Cocco from UCD (Ireland) presented the **citizen science** activities for environmental monitoring and adaptation planning. Through structured workshops, communities were trained to deploy and use **low-cost environmental sensors**, developed and catalogued within

the project, to collect hyper-local data on parameters such as air temperature, humidity, and water level. These activities enhanced public engagement, increased environmental literacy, and provided valuable data for researchers and planners. The **citizen science framework** combined participatory sensing with tools such as the Sensor Onboarding App and co-designed monitoring protocols, ensuring data quality and usability. This decentralized data collection approach not only complemented traditional scientific methods but also empowered communities as active participants in climate resilience building. Workshops helped them set up the sensors and use the data, making science more open and accessible. This empowered people not only to understand their surroundings but to shape the future of their cities.

Luís Campos Rodrigues from ENT (Spain), presented the **multi-criteria and cost-benefit evaluations** of ecosystem-based adaptation measures. One case study in **Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain)** involved restoring a 3-km section of a seasonal river to address urban flood risks. Using stakeholder workshops, several adaptation scenarios were assessed based on criteria including flood risk reduction, biodiversity, heat stress mitigation, and landscape aesthetics.

The **cost-benefit analysis (CBA)**, accounting for future climate scenarios and discount rates, demonstrated that nature-based interventions not only provided positive net present value (NPV) but also likely underestimated total benefits by excluding indirect and non-monetized effects, such as improved ecosystem services.

The results showed that combining green solutions with community involvement delivers strong, cost-effective protection.

During the following panel session, moderated by Rochelle Caruso from ERINN (Ireland), panelists discussed how, beyond technical achievements, SCORE's greatest contribution lies in its **legacy of engagement and institutional learning**. The project fostered enduring partnerships across academia, government, and civil society. The integrative co-creation process built **local capacity**, supported **policy mainstreaming**, and demonstrated how scientific innovation can be translated into actionable, community-driven climate adaptation.

Figure 2: Panel discussion at the SCORE final event

In summary, this first Session showcased how **interdisciplinary collaboration, participatory design, and nature-based thinking** can transform climate adaptation from a top-down technical challenge into a **shared, place-based innovation process**. It presents a replicable framework for cities worldwide aiming to blend technological advancement with community empowerment to address climate risks.

2.2. Data-Driven and Nature-Based Adaptation – Tools for Today and Tomorrow

Session 2 of the project's final event, titled *"Data-Driven and Nature-Based Adaptation – Tools for Today and Tomorrow"*, focused on showcasing how data, models, and digital tools can inform and guide effective disaster risk management strategies in urban coastal areas.

Figure 3: Second session at the SCORE final event

Paola Ceresa from RED Risk (Italy) presented the work done by several project partners, explaining how one of the objectives of the SCORE project was to develop of **comprehensive Disaster Risk Financing (DRF) framework**, designed to help cities understand, quantify, and manage climate-related risks, particularly those stemming from flooding. This framework covers the entire modeling chain, from gathering and downscaling climate data, to mapping hazards, assessing vulnerability and exposure, estimating risk and losses, and finally developing financial strategies to manage that risk.

This process began with the **selection of reliable, open-access climate datasets**, drawing on established European sources such as Copernicus and EMODnet, including both historical records and future climate projections, which were then **downscaled** to the local level to produce high-resolution, location-specific information relevant to urban planning and resilience efforts. With these localized datasets, the team generated **flood hazard maps** under different climate scenarios and return periods. These maps were then used to simulate the potential effects of extreme weather events, providing visual and quantitative tools for planning and risk communication. Importantly, the project explored how **Ecosystem-Based Adaptations (EBAs)**, like riparian reforestation, floodplain restoration, and riverbed excavation, can reduce both the extent of flooding and the overall risk to urban areas.

To understand the potential impact of such events, SCORE developed **harmonized exposure datasets** that cover buildings, infrastructure, and populations, complemented by advanced **vulnerability models**. These elements feed into risk assessments estimating potential **economic losses** under different scenarios, both with and without EBA interventions. The result is a nuanced understanding of **baseline and residual risk**, empowering stakeholders to compare outcomes and make informed decisions.

Paola Ceresa then presented a key innovation of the SCORE project, which is its emphasis on **financial resilience**. Beyond physical adaptation, cities must also be financially prepared for climate impacts. The project proposes a combination of **risk reduction, retention, and transfer strategies**, including insurance and contingency financing mechanisms. An integrated **optimization engine** helps align budgetary resources with risk mitigation goals, identifying financing gaps and prioritizing interventions.

Figure 4: Panel discussion at the SCORE final event

The session then continued with the presentation of the digital dimension of SCORE. Michele Sacco presented two powerful tools developed under SCORE: the **Digital Twin and Early Warning System (EWS)**, and the **SCORE ICT Platform (SIP)**. The Digital Twin offers a real-time, interactive simulation environment that supports emergency response and long-term planning. It can model flood scenarios, generate risk maps, and evaluate the effects of proposed adaptations. The SIP, on the other hand,

serves as a centralized data hub, integrating time series, spatial datasets, dashboards, and citizen-contributed sensor data. Together, these platforms promote **transparency, participation, and evidence-based decision making**.

During the following panel session, moderated by Giovanni Serafino from MBI Srl (Italy), panelists from different Coastal City Living Labs (CCLs), including Massa, Oarsoaldea, Vilanova i la Geltrú, Sligo, and Benidorm, presented how the tools and methodologies developed under SCORE have been adapted to local conditions, providing concrete examples of how integrated data and nature-based solutions can bolster climate resilience at the municipal level.

The concluding remarks emphasized how SCORE not only supported cities in coping with current risks, but it **enabled proactive, forward-looking adaptation**. By merging science, technology, and local knowledge, the project offered a powerful model for coastal resilience, one that can be scaled and replicated across Europe and beyond.

2.3. SCORE exhibition booth

Alongside its final event, the SCORE project hosted a dedicated booth at the ECCA 2025 conference on 17–18 June. The booth aimed to engage conference attendees, foster connections with stakeholders focused on coastal climate adaptation, and showcase the key outcomes and accomplishments from four years of collaborative research and fieldwork.

Figure 5: Visitors and demonstrations at the SCORE booths

At the booth, visitors could explore a range of communication materials, including a project roll-up summarising SCORE’s mission and approach, the agenda of our final workshop, the schedule of our live demo sessions, as well as various dissemination material, such as:

- The newly released **final brochure** with information on key achievements, policy briefs, scientific publications and collaborations resulting from four years of work supporting climate resilience in coastal communities.
- The **final media press kit** with information on and including the final press release, as well as the main tools and platforms developed by the project, an overview of each of the 10 CCLs, as well as some key numbers and great pictures.
- A “**Lessons learned**” document offering practical guidance drawn from the ten SCORE Coastal City Living Labs (CCLs) on how best to create, implement, and evaluate a Coastal City Living Lab.
- A document gathering targeted **policy recommendations** tailored to EU policymakers, offering practical guidance on integrating Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) measures, participatory planning, the living lab approach, and innovative technical and financial tools into existing policy and planning frameworks.

Figure 6: Flyer planning live demos station at the SCORE booth

These materials offered an accessible and comprehensive overview of SCORE's outcomes, from overall project highlights to specific results from each of the 10 CCLLs, with a focus on local actions and key lessons learned over the past four years.

To showcase SCORE's technological outputs in a more hands-on way, we also organised a series of live demo sessions throughout the day on Tuesday, 17 June. A dedicated demo agenda was available at the booth, allowing participants to choose the sessions they wished to attend. The programme was divided into four 90-minute slots covering different topics:

1. Co-creation and citizen science tools
2. The SCORE Data Platform
3. Early Warning System and Digital Twin Platform, with its various features
4. Models and resulting hazard maps, from regional to urban scale, addressing flood hazards

These interactive demonstrations provided a valuable opportunity for attendees to engage with project partners, test the tools in real time, and discover how these innovations contribute to enhancing climate resilience in European coastal cities, while fostering community involvement in decision-making processes.

3. EVENT PROMOTION

3.1. SCORE website and social media

The promotion of the SCORE Final Event started in early May 2025 with the publication of a Save the date on the SCORE website and social media.

A dedicated news article was also published on the SCORE website (<https://score-eu-project.eu/2025/05/14/scores-final-event-at-ecca-2025/>) and widely promoted on the SCORE social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram and Facebook). This communication included a registration link to the ECCA Conference since, as for all ECCA side events, official registration for the conference was required to attend the SCORE final event.

Once the final agenda was validated by all project partners, the website has been updated to include the detailed workshop programme along with its official title. A second announcement was then disseminated via all SCORE social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram) to widely promote the workshop's detailed agenda to our target audiences.

Figure 7: Invitation message sent to SCORE newsletter subscriber

To maximise participation in the event, it was decided on the last week before the event, to create a Teams connection link, allowing people who were unable to travel to Rimini to attend the workshop remotely.

This information was widely shared across all social media channels of the project and the partners' networks to inform the SCORE community about the opportunity to join the event online. At the same time, the project website was updated with a dedicated registration form, enabling interested participants to sign up and follow the workshop remotely.

Several posts were published on LinkedIn in the period May-June 2025, collecting almost 1500 impressions, with posts on LinkedIn reaching over 1700 persons, bringing wide visibility to the project itself.

The event was also promoted through a dedicated message sent on June 4, 2025 to 587 newsletter subscribers: [SCORE Final Event at ECCA 2025 - Join us in Rimini!](#)

Figure 8: Examples of posts on social media

3.2. Other channels

SCORE final event was announced on the news section of the ECCA conference: <https://www.ecca2025.eu/news/side-events-at-ecca2025.htm>.

SCORE partners and CLLs actively participated in the dissemination of the event. The event was announced by several SCORE partners through their respective networks, websites, and social media.

To maximise its visibility, the news was also sent to relevant European networks, helping us reach a wider and more varied public. The event was announced, for example, in the CINEA (https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/events/european-climate-change-adaptation-2025-2025-06-16_en) and ClimateAdapt (<https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/more-events/innovative-solutions-for-climate-change-adaptation-in-coastal-areas-when-green-and-digital-tools-meet-living-labs-score-final-project-event>) websites, as well as promoted through the Coastal list on Gmail.

4. PARTICIPANTS

Approximately 50 participants attended the SCORE final event in person. As they were already registered for the ECCA conference, no separate registration was required for our session, and therefore we do not have detailed information about their profiles.

23 people from 10 different countries (Belgium, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Kenya, Pakistan, Portugal, Spain and Türkiye) registered online to attend the event remotely. The Figure below illustrates participant categories, indicating that the majority came from academia, followed by government bodies.

Figure 9: Online participants categories at the SCORE final event

5. CONCLUSIONS

One of the key objectives of the SCORE Final event was to share the project's main achievements and lessons learned after four years of collaborative work, while engaging with a broad community of professionals involved in climate adaptation for coastal areas. By organising this event within the framework of ECCA 2025, SCORE was able to connect with decision-makers, researchers, practitioners, and Living Lab facilitators from across Europe and beyond.

APPENDIX: PICTURES OF SCORE AT ECCA2025

Smart control of the climate resilience in European coastal cities

SCORE aims to develop a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs) addressing water and climate-related hazards to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities using an integrated approach of smart technologies and nature-based solutions.

28
partners
CONSORTIUM

12
countries
CONSORTIUM

4
years
DURATION

01.07.21
30.06.25
start-end
DATE

10M
euros
BUDGET

Coastal City Living Labs (CCLs)

SCORE is establishing a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' that will involve citizens, scientists, policy makers and other stakeholders in providing prototype coastal city early-warning systems.

Silgo
IRELAND

Dublin
IRELAND

Gdańsk
POLAND

Piran
SLOVENIA

Basque country
SPAIN

Benidorm
SPAIN

Province of
Vilanova i la Geltrú
SPAIN

Massa
ITALY

Samsun
TURKEY

Oeiras
PORTUGAL

Expected outcomes

- Baseline risk analysis and mapping of extreme climate impacts and sea level rise
- Citizen science solutions for climate change monitoring
- Coastal City Living Lab (CCLs) design, implementation and evaluation framework and lessons learned
- A new database containing the processed data and the main SCORE outcomes
- A software for the design and evaluation of financial resilience strategies
- Socio-economic assessment of EBA interventions and policy recommendations
- Climatic downscaling methods, data and uncertainties
- Models for coastal hazard predictions

